

USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

¹Qutbedinov A., ²Mavlonova Y.

¹Professor, Navoiy state pedagogical institute

²Senior teacher, Navoiy state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7785626>

Abstract. *In this article, was given qualitative analysis of the development of students' professional competence is analyzed using decoder and ORES methods. Problems related to scientific-theoretical specific aspects and their scientific-methodological solutions are described.*

Keywords: *student, competence, decoder, concepts, educational efficiency, technology, problems, solutions.*

It is known that President, Shavkat Mirziyoev, in his address speech to the Oliy Majlis on December 20, announced 2023 as the year of "Attention to people and quality education"¹. This is a proof that the priority of the state policy in our republic is to ensure the interests of people. This, in turn, imposes the responsibility of bringing the educational system to the level of quality.

"The Concept of Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", adopted on the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5712 of April 29, 2019, defines the main trends in the development of technology education.

In particular, improvement of the field of education based on the experience of setting standards in the field of education of developed foreign countries, taking into account national characteristics and reforms implemented in the country;

- to ensure compliance of the requirements of the state educational standard of technology science with the international requirements for the quality of education and personnel training;
- qualitatively updating the content of technology science, as well as improving the teaching methodology, gradually applying the principles of individualization to the educational process;
- organization of the status of technology science, its mutual integration with other sciences, and career orientation of students;
- the content of technology science, the formation of technological literacy, critical thinking and creativity competencies that can be applied in independent life;
- development of variable educational modules in the teaching of technology;
- wide introduction of effective forms, methods and means of educating students on the basis of national, universal and spiritual values into the educational process;
- introduction of digital technologies and modern methods into the technology education process;
- implementation of innovative pedagogical and modern information and communication technologies to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of the educational process;

Therefore, the science of technology and its teaching methodology includes: providing all-round theoretical and practical knowledge to future teachers, improving the consistency of providing information about professions in the primary classes of general education schools, the requirements of the State Education Standards include the tasks of imparting theoretical and

practical knowledge. The science of technology and its teaching methods is considered a subject of the educational methods course, based on the results of the main scientific researches of the science, enriched with advanced pedagogical experiences and based on materials based on modern technologies. Preparing students for practical technological processes and ensuring that they acquire the skills and abilities of basic technological operations.

The teaching content of technological education must be constantly updated so that, firstly, it does not lag behind the achievements of the science of technological education, and secondly, it corresponds to the needs of society. Currently, it is important to choose the content that requires a fundamental approach, that is, the content of education should include the development of the learner, the satisfaction of his requests, and the ability to independently determine himself. , he should get all of them. It is necessary for a technological education teacher to know the criteria and signs of content selection. With a sense of responsibility, it is necessary to pay great attention to the methodological approach of teaching in the classroom using non-traditional methods, requiring the organization of technological education, differentiation of content, its individualization and optimization. Acquiring the methodology of activity in the teaching of technological education can be the main organizer of the organization of the educational process without denying the system of knowledge, skills and qualifications.

One of such innovative methods is the Decoder method, the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin alphabet is determined in the order of numerical sequence. This method is based on the integration approach of teaching, which connects the science of technology with the science of the mother tongue.

For example: If we take the topic of studying the properties of metals and alloys, the terms in this topic are metals. 12, 4, 19, 1, 11, 11, that is, the word metal comes from. Here there is the letter m after the number 12, the letter e after the number 4, the letter t after the number 19, the letter a after the number 1, and the letter l after the number 11. In this case, we can mix the numbers. If the letters 12, 19, 4, 17, 8 M, T, E, R, I are mixed, we will correct them. The word T E M I R is formed. We can use this method in other subjects as well.

Another such method is F.S.M.U. this method is to teach students to express their opinions on related issues during the discussion of the topic being studied in the training, to show the reasons justifying these opinions, to give examples that confirm them, and finally to draw general conclusions, and is a training method. This method helps students to think freely, to defend their opinion and to convey their opinion to others, to openly argue, to develop a culture of debate, as well as to analyze and assimilate the knowledge acquired by students in the educational process. teaches to determine and evaluate the level. General scheme of the method ORES:

- O– express your opinion;
- R – give a reason justifying your opinion;
- E – give an example confirming your reason;
- S – summarize your point.

An example of using the method in practice of ORES:

The teacher prepares handouts with tasks like the following in advance and distributes them to small groups or individual students during the lesson. The teacher announces the time to complete the task. Performs general leadership during the performance of duties. After the students have completed the tasks assigned to them, they organize their general discussion. Those who perform the task best are encouraged.

For example: "ORES" technology for the topic "WOODEN MATERIALS"

Opinion	Wood and wood materials are widely used in all sectors of the economy.
Reason	The reason for the wide use of wooden materials is their high technical properties and ease of use
Example	Construction and constructions, automotive industry, wagon industry, chemical and idol industry, paper pulp industry, plywood, furniture, sports inventory, fall production, ethyl alcohol, paint production
Summarize	Currently, wood processing enterprises are producing new types of wood materials with higher mechanical properties and are widely used in various sectors of the national economy. The exterior of the wood is beautiful, well-glued and well-finished.

From the above methods, it can be concluded that in the continuous education system of educational goals, through the qualitative analysis of innovative methods, the development of educational tasks that can perform the logical sequence of natural phenomena, especially thinking and generalization, and the formation of logical thinking skills in technological lessons of their mental operations: allows teaching to use such as analysis and synthesis in the process of thinking.

The advantage and efficiency of innovative methods is that students not only express their opinions on ideas, views and debates in classes, but also activate their huge informational potential and are full of their strength in the competition related to the positive task in the educational process. requires the use: the intellectual power of a group is always higher than the amount of intellectual power of a single student.

REFERENCES

1. Address speech of the President of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis. <https://oz.sputniknews-uz.com/20221220>
2. SH.O.Toshpulatova.Innovative methods in teaching physics// Guided book. – T.: «Ta’lim taraqqiyoti»,2017. -.255p.
3. Ishmukhamedov R.J., Yuldashev M. Innovative pedagogical technologies in education and upbringing.– T.: “Nihol”, 2016.-279 p.
4. Tahirov O'.O. The methodology of introducing the state educational standard and curriculum into educational practice.// Guided book. –T. : PTM, 2017. - 72 p.
5. Qutbeddinov A., Toshpulatova Sh.O., Mavlonova Y.I. Bo ‘lajak fizika fani o‘qituvchilarining mantiqiy savodxonligini rivojlantirishda PISA dasturidan foydalanish. –T. : O‘zbekiston respublikasi xalq ta’limi vazirligining ilmiy-metodik jurnal. 2022. №5. B.38-48